

Youth, Culture & Sports

September 2023

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region's economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda is monitored by the project POLICY ANSWERS, and the wider context and progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this brief report card, you find a first outline of the baseline data collected during 2022 and the first months of 2023.

In terms of Youth, Culture and Sport, the monitoring focuses, on the one hand, on the context indicator "Youth with above basic overall digital skills in 2021" and, on the other hand, on a variety of achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see on the backside of this document).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Youth with above basic overall digital skills in 2021 (in percent)

The indicator gives the percentage of individuals (aged 16 to 29) whose information and data literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, safety, and problem-solving skills are above basic level.

Source

Eurostat, <https://tinyurl.com/sourceeustat> (accessed 25 January 2023)

Note

Data for Kosovo* not available

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Priority

Fostering cooperation in the areas of youth, sports and culture

Regional Indicators

Regional policy dialogue on culture			
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Legend: Information not available

WB Economy Indicators

Performance of the WB economy: information not provided

	Integration & stronger participation in EU programmes and initiatives		Fostered capacity building for R&I, education and VET	
	Full association in E+ programme			
Albania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + A number of projects and mobilities implemented - Progress towards becoming programming country 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidelines available, not specified in number - No twinning projects, no TAIEX missions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Involvement in the initiative - Number of stakeholders included not specified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Week of sport organised - Number of participants & partnering organisations not specified
Bosnia and Herzegovina	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + A number of projects and mobilities implemented - Progress towards becoming programming country 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + TAIEX missions - No twinning projects - Information on guidelines and Technical Assistance projects not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No involvement in the initiative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Week of sport organised by a number of partnering organisations - Number of participants not specified
Kosovo*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + A number of projects and mobilities implemented - Progress towards becoming programming country 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Twinning project in place, guideline under development - No TAIEX missions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Involvement in the initiative - Number of stakeholders involved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Week of sport organised - Number of participants & partnering organisations not specified
Montenegro	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No progress towards becoming programming country - Information on projects and mobilities not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Involvement in the initiative, number of stakeholders involved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Week of sport organised with large number of participants - Number of partnering organisations not specified
North Macedonia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + A number of projects implemented - Progress towards becoming programming country - Number of mobilities not specified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + TAIEX mission organised - No twinning projects - Information on guidelines not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No involvement in the initiative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Week of sport organised with large number of participants and partnering organisations
Serbia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + A number of projects implemented - Progress towards becoming programming country - Number of mobilities not specified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guidelines available, not specified in number - Information on twinning projects & TAIEX missions not provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No involvement in the initiative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Week of sport organised with large number of participants and partnering organisations

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